

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 1.2

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies

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Deliverable Number	D1.2
Work Package	WP1
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable leader	AAFC
Due date	31 July 2021
Submission date	20 August 2021
Version	V1
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000349 (ALL-Ready).

History of changes

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
V0	July 2021	ALL-Ready partners	Improvements

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List of abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
WP	Work Package

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Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European Network of living labs and research infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This document lists criteria and indicators to identify organisations for possible inclusion in the future Network of living labs and research infrastructures for an agroecology transition in Europe. The criteria and indicators seek to be applicable to a range of organisations that could strengthen the transition to agroecology in Europe. These include organisations:

1. that are already actively involved in the agroecology transition;
2. whose involvement in the agroecology transition could be accelerated by their belonging to the Network;
3. whose involvement in the Network will be beneficial to other Network members, thereby accelerating the agroecology transition.

The criteria focus on the activities and values of the organisations rather than their descriptions or establishment histories. This strategy was chosen in order to ensure that the mapping exercise in WP2 is able to include organisations that function as agroecology living labs or research infrastructures even if these organisations do not use such a terminology to describe their activities. The criteria aim to be inclusive of positions at all points of the food system (e.g., production, processing, distribution, consumption). The method was the following: a first set of criteria were identified by compiling key recommendations for agroecology transition from diverse relevant sources (see References) using the same conceptual framework based on the correspondence between the agroecology principles and the unique features of living labs and research infrastructures (deliverable 1.1). This set was then submitted to evaluation and completion during a 2-hour stakeholder workshop with around 100 participants (representing farmers associations, funding agencies, academics, representatives of food industry, and others). The criteria were then finalised through a series of exchanges between WP1.2 interdisciplinary expert group.

These criteria were built with a view to focusing, delimiting and standardising the mapping, analysis and principles of agroecological transition processes in WP2. All the inclusion criteria focus on functional characteristics of the organisations, and not whether they label themselves as living labs, research infrastructure or use the term “agroecology”. Therefore, they will be useful to capture the picture the current situation in Europe in terms of agroecology relevant living labs and similar open innovation arrangements (OIAs), as well as research infrastructures. Furthermore, organisations might be identified that already show or could in the future be important participants in a wider network of organisations that work towards an agroecology transition process.

The criteria could be used to:

- determine the inclusion/exclusion boundaries for the Network. For example, in the construction of a questionnaire for the mapping of agroecology transition actors in Europe (WP2), the inclusion requirement could be that a respondent fulfils at least one indicator activity for each criterion.
- enhance understanding of the agroecology transition in Europe. For example, the criteria can be used to understand which aspects of the transition are being

prioritised by actors already and which need further attention to achieve a holistic development.

- evaluate the progress of the transition and of the Network specifically. For example, the criteria could be used in the design of repeated surveys of Network members to highlight areas which require further support, or specific gaps in the Network which could be filled by the inclusion of specific additional actors.

1. Criteria and indicators

1.1 Approach/Governance

The organisation's activities include or support the **co-creation of innovation and knowledge**.

The organisation:

- Connects with farmers to co-create knowledge
- Promotes participatory and multi-stakeholder approaches
- Promotes co-creation of innovation (technological, environmental, social, or economic) Adopts a phased, lifecycle approach in its innovation activities (e.g., ideation, co-creation, experimentation, and validation)
- Encourages active involvement of users
- Considers the user's real-life context (e.g., innovations are tested where users would actually use them, such as on-farm testing of agroecology practices)
- Is place-based (embedded within a broader community, landscape, region, or other geographical or socio-spatial context)
- Conducts research and education in the field
- Promotes diversity of facilities, data production and context that allow scientific production and references for stakeholders
- Promotes social learning
- Evaluates and adjusts (on an ongoing basis) in response to evolving contexts and the expected and unexpected results and effects of what is co-created

1.2 Objectives/Vision

The organisation promotes **resilience and sustainability**.

The organisation:

- Supports systemic resilience of agroecosystems to climate change, extreme weather events and other disturbances
- Supports systemic resilience and adaptive capacity to changing environmental conditions due to climate change
- Supports supply chain and livelihood resilience (through e.g. including considerations of profit and profitability in transition practices)
- Uses a long-term, long-lasting strategy and approach

The organisation supports **diversity**.

The organisation:

- Considers diversity from plot to landscape and to territory
- Considers diversity from crops/animals to products
- Improves local seed/breed diversity
- Involves various actors involved throughout the value or production chain

- Integrates locally adapted crops/breeds/products
- Considers the development and improvement of new or existing practices, such as crop rotation
- Includes spatially diversified farms through a multi-habitat approach
- Promotes biodiversity at all spatial levels
- Promotes diversification of diets and consumption

1.3 Principles

The organisation supports **climate change adaptation and mitigation and environmental adaptation** of agricultural practices.

The organisation:

- Considers biological and Integrated pest management
- Considers cover crops for improved soil conditions
- Considers perennial crops
- Considers reduced tillage
- Considers adoption of organic and low-input farming (e.g., reduced use of water, nutrients, or pesticides)
- Considers protection of domestic pollinators
- Considers improved animal welfare and health
- Considers other landscape planning and synchronised landscape activity leading to improved agricultural ecosystem services
- Considers climate mitigation through system redesign and practices that sequester carbon and reduce greenhouse gas emissions

The organisation promotes **synergies between different ecosystem functions**.

The organisation:

- Is involved in producing non-crop plants to enhance biodiversity
- Takes an integrated and system-wide perspective
- Is involved in agroforestry, rotational/regenerative grazing, or integrated crop-livestock systems
- Is involved in other combinations/integrations at the farm level to optimise (ecological) synergies
- Supports integrated pest management by habitat manipulation

1.4 Activities

The organisation promotes **efficiency** in the use of natural resources.

The organisation:

- Promotes reduced water consumption

- Promotes reduced application of pesticides, veterinary drugs and fertiliser
- Promotes reduced energy use
- Promotes reduced waste production
- Promotes improved plant variety and animal breed

The organisation is involved in responsible **management and use of natural resources**.

The organisation:

- It promotes alternative (non-chemical) soil and agronomic inputs (e.g. green manure)
- It supports the recycling of waste water
- It promotes the use of biomass residues for energy generation
- It promotes climate change mitigation through land management practices (e.g. carbon farming)
- It is involved in other practices that enhance the responsible use and recycling of biomass and organic matter

1.5 Values and “living values”

The organisation is involved in creating **circular and solidarity economies**

The organisation:

- Provides business support for shortening value chains
- Supports regional value generation through food
- Encourages demand for seasonal and regional products
- Supports the creation of “good jobs” in the agri-food sector

The organisation is focused on **values of social and ecological justice**.

The organisation:

- Supports gender equality and vulnerable and disadvantaged groups
- Promotes such values as equity, dignity, inclusion
- Supports rights to food (sufficient, accessible, adequate)
- Promotes food sovereignty
- Supports the right to healthy, adequate, diversified and culturally appropriate food traditions and diets
- Works according to open science principles

Acknowledgements

We thank the partners of ALL-Ready for their critical reviews of these criteria and their comments to improve them.

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